

An unsupervised damage detection method for an operating wind turbine blade

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Abstract. Continuous dynamic monitoring offers a valuable opportunity for the long-term assessment of the health and integrity of civil structures. However, dealing with the high dimensionality and data sparsity resulting from extended monitoring periods and the challenges posed by environmental and operational variability (EOVs) is crucial. To address these issues, this paper proposes an unsupervised method for reducing dimensional space to detect damages in an operating V27 WTB under varying EOVs. The study utilizes data collected from accelerometers installed on one of the blades at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). Initially, various time-domain, frequency-domain, and time-frequency domain features are employed to capture potential information from the time-series data. Subsequently, principal component analysis (PCA) is utilized to reduce dimensional space. The study validates the performance of the dimensional reduction space set of features through commonly used unsupervised learning methods, particularly the One-Class Support Vector Machine (OC-SVM). The findings of this study contribute to the development of effective methods for structural health monitoring of wind turbine blades, addressing challenges posed by environmental and operational variability.

Keywords: Onshore Wind turbines, Health monitoring, Unsupervised learning, Environmental and operational variables.

Introduction

The declining costs of wind-generated electricity have positioned it as one of the most economically viable green energy options [1]. However, as wind turbine blades (WTBs) grow in size to meet increasing demands for wind power generation, they encounter challenges from environmental factors such as dynamic loads and precipitation, resulting in defects like cracks and delamination [2]. Timely detection and addressing of these defects are imperative for maintaining operational efficiency and preventing major failures [3]. Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) methods based on vibration, known for their reliability, operate on the principle that any adverse changes in a structure due to damage will significantly alter its vibration responses. These methods utilize Damage Sensitive Features (DSFs) derived from these responses to assess the structural condition [4]. They are broadly categorized into data-driven and model-driven approaches. While model-driven methods rely on accurate structural models but necessitate frequent updates to match real-world conditions

[5], data-driven approaches such as statistical pattern recognition utilize vibration responses to effectively monitor structural integrity. These methods ensure the safe and dependable operation of wind energy systems, as evidenced by numerous studies [6, 7].

Due to the high dimensionality of raw acceleration data, data-driven SHM techniques utilize Feature Extraction (FE) to convert raw data into a format suitable for Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, aiding in identifying features correlating with damage [8]. This process involves analyzing data in various domains, such as time, frequency, or time-frequency, and leveraging ML algorithms to extract relevant information [9-12]. However, extracted features may also capture non-damage-related changes in the system's response. In real-life wind turbine applications, ensuring accurate damage diagnosis during operation is crucial due to the influence of varying Environmental and Operational Variables (EOVs) like temperature, wind excitation, and rotational speed on blade dynamics, complicating detection efforts [13]. Under such circumstances, EOVs can alter the inherent physical properties of a wind turbine structure along with its vibration responses or features. These changes, similar to those created by damage, may lead to misleading results in the damage detection process [14]. To accurately distinguish between DSFs from undamaged and damaged structures, various strategies are employed, typically divided into supervised and unsupervised learning [15-17]. Supervised learning methods rely on labeled data for training and testing, potentially limiting their real-world application due to label availability. Unsupervised techniques are usually trained using data from a healthy structure [18].

One commonly used unsupervised approach for mitigating EOVs is principal component analysis (PCA), applied for dimensionality reduction and extensively used in damage detection [19]. For instance, Yan et al. [20] projected their feature vectors onto the sub-space of minor principal components (PCs) and employed these components as damage indicators, assuming that major PCs were dominated by EOVs. However, many unsupervised methods assume linear correlations in vibration features, which may not hold under the influence of EOVs. To address non-linear effects, Reynders et al. [21] introduced a kernel-based PCA, identifying a non-linear environmental model. They found that linear PCA failed to differentiate between damaged and healthy conditions, while non-linear PCA enabled damage detection. However, selecting the best PCs to mitigate EOVs remains challenging. To validate to accurately distinguish between corresponding dimensionality reduction space obtained from PCA from undamaged and damaged structures, anomaly detection strategies are employed. The One-Class Support Vector Machine (OC-SVM) learning, as an anomaly detection method, offers various advantages. It is fully non-parametric, allowing for accurate descriptions of data that do not adhere to a probability density function. Additionally, it is capable of generating non-linear, flexible boundaries with reduced computational effort [22].

This paper proposes an unsupervised method for reducing the dimensional space to detect damages in an operating V27 WTB under EOV conditions. The turbine is located at the campus of the DTU, with data measured at variable operating conditions (e.g., various rotor speeds) under healthy and three damaged conditions using 12 accelerometers installed on one of the blades. The primary goal is to identify an effective and minimal space set, addressing concerns about the reliability and robustness of models in recognizing damage extent. Initially, twelve time-domain, fifteen frequency-domain, and fifteen time-frequency domain features are utilized to capture potential information from the time-series data. Subsequently, PCA as an unsupervised methodology is employed to reduce dimensional space. The study validates the performance of the optimal space set of features, PCs, by employing commonly used anomaly detection methods such as OC-SVM.

Experimental setup

The study utilized experimental data from a monitoring campaign on a 225 kW Vestas V27 wind turbine near Roskilde, Denmark. Equipped with 12 accelerometers and an electro-mechanical actuator, one blade underwent artificial damage by adjusting trailing edge openings. This led to five health states: undamaged, 15 cm, 30 cm, and 45 cm openings, and a repaired state, which are depicted in **Figure 1**. Monitoring occurred over 104 days, recording blade vibration responses every 5 minutes. The data acquisition system, including a DC accelerometer in the spinner, wirelessly transmitted data to a tower computer. Approximately 25,000 excitation/response datasets were collected, focusing on the 43 rpm operational regime. Of these, 856 observations represented the healthy state, with 15 cm, 30 cm, and 45 cm damaged states comprising 158, 193, and 132 observations, respectively. During actuator hits, each accelerometer recorded about 500,000 data samples, filtered using a band-pass filter with cutoff frequencies of 700 and 1200 Hz. Filtered signals were then aligned to the 300 samples displaying the highest amplitudes during actuator hits. For additional details, reference Tcherniak and Mølgaard [13].

Figure 1. The schematic diagram of the WT blade (not to scale) shows the location of the actuator (green circle), sensors (red circles), and damage locations (grey tone rectangles). The main spar is indicated by dashed lines (dimensions in mm).

The damage detection framework

Feature Extraction

This study extracts statistical, temporal, and spectral features from acceleration responses, detailed in **Table 1**. Statistical features capture fundamental signal characteristics, calculated using formulas considering signal and time vectors, sampling frequency, signal length, and state probability. Temporal features represent signal dynamics over time, including equations like Δx (discrete derivative) with temporal discretization through integration over the time step (Δt). Spectral time-frequency features illustrate signal changes in the frequency domain over time, utilizing Short Term Fourier Transform (STFT) to derive time-frequency domain representations [23]. To address spectral leakage inherent in feature extraction algorithms, a Tukey window with a 12.5% overlap is applied. For further details on the features used, refer to Tadj et al [24].

Table 1. Time-, frequency-, and time-frequency domain features.

Statistical Features	Temporal Features	Spectral Features
Min	Absolute Energy	Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) mean coefficient
Max	The area under the curve	Fundamental Frequency
Median	Centroid	Maximum Frequency
Mean	Entropy	Median Frequency
Standard Deviation	Mean Absolute Differences	Max Power Spectrum

Variance	Mean Differences	Spectral Centroid
Skewness	Median Absolute Differences	Spectral Spread
Kurtosis	Median Differences	Spectral Skewness
Mean Absolute Deviation	Peak-to-Peak Distance	Spectral Kurtosis
Median Absolute Deviation	Signal Distance	Spectral Slope
Root Mean Square (RMS)	Slope	Spectral Distance
Interquartile Range (IR)	Sum Absolute Differences	Spectral Entropy
	Total Energy	Power Bandwidth
	Zero Crossing Rate	Spectral Decrease
	Neighbourhood Peaks	Spectral Variance

Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a technique for compressing dimensions while minimizing information loss. It achieves this by mapping feature vectors from the original feature space to a low-dimensional space that captures the largest variance. Conventionally, PCA organizes the components such that the first PC is associated with the highest contribution to the overall variance of the feature vector, the second component with the second highest, and so on [25]. PCA can be used as a tool to eliminate components governed by EOVs. Additionally, the feature vector undergoes re-scaling through z-score normalization. This normalization method scales features according to their distance from the mean in terms of standard deviation. As a result, the standardized dataset has a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, preserving the shape characteristics of the original features.

Anomaly Detection

The support vector machine algorithm is primarily a supervised learning method tailored for two-class classification tasks, establishing a hyperplane to distinguish data into separate classes. An extension of this, introduced by Schölkopf et al. [26], is the OC-SVM algorithm, devised to tackle one-class classification challenges. In OC-SVM, data undergoes mapping to a feature space utilizing an appropriate kernel function, intending to place most of it in a non-zero region. In this framework, the origin signifies the sole member of the non-target class, treated as an outlier. Subsequently, the mapped vectors are delineated from the origin with the maximum margin, achieved by solving a quadratic programming problem [22].

Evaluation metrics

In this study, the classification threshold is fine-tuned to minimize false alarms and avoid missed alarms through the utilization of thresholds derived from training models. The training data is partitioned into diverse segments, within each of which the mean and skewness are computed. The threshold value is subsequently determined by adding the mean to the skewness raised to a power. Ultimately, the optimal threshold is attained by averaging across all segments. Then, the confusion matrix serves as an evaluation metric for new observations, comparing true and predicted results, where correct predictions are represented by diagonal elements and mismatches by off-diagonal elements. Precision, recall, and F1-score are defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$F1 - score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where TP, FP, FN, and TN are true positive, false positive, false negative, and true negative, respectively [27].

Results and discussions

In this section, the proposed framework is evaluated using the dataset explained in the previous section. The objective is to identify the reduced-dimensional space sets of features that maximize anomaly detection performance.

Feature Extraction

For each measurement, the 42 features previously discussed are extracted from signals gathered by 12 sensors, totaling 504 features (12 sensors \times 42 features). There are 1339 observations in all states, encompassing both the healthy state and damaged states, resulting in a large matrix comprising 1339 \times 504, different domain features.

Principal Component Analysis

A reduced representation size of the feature vectors is achieved by applying PCA to the set of feature vectors obtained from all sensors. The PCs are computed using the training set. A common number of PCs for analysis is chosen to ensure that at least 95% of the total variance of the features is retained, resulting in a selection of 99 components (as shown in **Figure 2**). The remaining dimensions are categorized as part of the noise PC subspace [19].

Figure 2. Cumulative Variance of different number of components.

Anomaly Detection

In this evaluation, the dimensional features space include vector $f^{(k)} \in R^{1 \times q}$, which contains q , PCA-D features, for observation k . The matrix of features $f^{(k)} \in R^{r \times q}$ is defined as follows:

$$F = [f^{(1)} f^{(2)} \dots f^{(k)} \dots f^{(r)}] \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where r is the number of observations. The PCA-D features are used to train the anomaly detection algorithms based on various PCs with different kernel functions. The features are

split into training $f_{tr}^{hl} \in F^{u \times q}$ and testing $F_{ts} \in F^{m \times q}$, where u is the number of training and m the number of testing observations. The testing set F_{ts} contains a subset of healthy f_{ts}^{hl} and damaged f_{ts}^{dam} observations of the structure. The split of the features for training and testing is visualized in **Figure 3**. The matrix consists of 1339 observations with $F \in R^{1339 \times PCs}$.

Figure 3. Data partitioning for anomaly detection methodologies.

The PCA-D feature vectors for training the OC-SVM consist of the extracted coefficients in this section. The OC-SVM requires two user-assigned parameters. The first, ν , regulates the false positive rate and was set to 0.05. The second parameter, σ , governing the Gaussian kernel, requires careful selection to avoid overfitting or underfitting. Bayesian optimization is utilized to find optimal kernel values for each sensor. The Damage Index (DI) is computed from the anomaly scores produced by the OC-SVM model, offering a quantitative measure of damage severity. Subsequently, the optimal threshold is determined using the training data, calculated as the average of mean plus the square of skewness within each of the 20 parts into which the training data is divided. Similarly, the PCs are obtained based on capturing 0.95% total variance of all features. To assess the performance of the selected PCs, the classification accuracy of various kernel functions is examined using the 99 PCs, as presented in **Table 2**. The results show the accuracy of Polynomial Kernel with $G = 2$ has a higher value compared to other kernel functions.

Table 2. F1 score of different kernels and gamma in PCA for OC-SVM in num component = 99.

	Polynomial Kernel			Gaussian Kernel			Sigmoid Kernel		
	G=1	G=2	G=3	G=1	G=2	G=3	G=1	G=2	G=3
OC-SVM	70.27	90.82	82.67	32.17	32.63	31.97	35.01	35.07	34.05

To obtain the minimal dimensional feature space with high accuracy, various PCs are evaluated corresponding to a Polynomial Kernel with $G = 2$. As depicted in **Table 3**, reducing the feature space dimensionality leads to an increase in the classification accuracy of OC-SVM algorithms, indicating that the first PCs are more sensitive to damage. For further evaluation, the results of PCs = 99 and 5 are illustrated in **Figure 4**.

Table 3. The F1-score (%) of OC-SVM inputting Polynomial Kernel PCA with Gamma (G) =2 in various PCs.

Num of Component	99	80	60	40	20	10	5
OC-SVM (G = 2)	90.82	89.56	93.47	96.05	94.56	97.23	99.36

The primary challenge in selecting the minimal PCs lies in finding the right balance between sensitivity to damage and insensitivity to EOVs. As shown in **Figure 4**, choosing a higher number of PCs reveals a noticeable trend with increasing damage states, but also correlates strongly with EOVs in healthy datasets. Conversely, selecting only a few first PCs, such as 5, eliminates the influence of EOVs on healthy datasets, it succeeds in anomaly detection with high accuracy, approximately 99.36%, but exhibits a significant gap between healthy datasets and early damage states, like the 15cm damaged state compared to other extended damage states. Therefore, it is critical to identify the optimal PCs for damage

detection and EOV mitigation, which requires further investigation as part of ongoing research efforts.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. The results of OC-SVM with PCs of a) 99 and b) 5.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study addresses the challenges of SHM in WTBs by proposing an unsupervised method for detecting damages under varying environmental and operational conditions. By utilizing data collected from accelerometers installed on a WTB at the DTU, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of employing time-domain, frequency-domain, and time-frequency domain features followed by PCA for dimensional reduction. The performance of the reduced feature set is validated using OC-SVM as an anomaly detection. By effectively addressing the challenges posed by high-dimensional and sparse data, as well as environmental and operational variability, this research contributes to the advancement of anomaly detection techniques for wind turbine blades. However, finding the optimal PCs to create a balance between distinguishing different damage states and mitigating EOVs remains a challenge to needs further investigation.

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